

A MECHATRONICS APPROACH FOR ACTIVE CONTROL OF HYDROSTATIC THRUST BEARING USING FOPID CONTROL TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

The current research presents nonlinear mathematical model of hydrostatic thrust bearing which has been controlled with help of mechatronics control techniques. Mechatronics approach plays an important role to develop active hydrostatic thrust bearings which have advantage of better dynamics characteristics due to feedback control system. Nonlinear mathematical model of hydrostatic thrust bearing has been divided into three subsystems, each subsystem depends on the type of input. The performance of hydrostatic thrust bearing is checked under different types of inputs such as supply pressure, viscosity and recess pressure. The fractional-order PID control method is employed to enhance tracking accuracy and ensure system stability. Simulations are performed in Matlab/Simulink and results are compared with published literature. Effectiveness of proposed study is verified by comparing results with published literature under different types of input and dynamics conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of mechatronics techniques is gaining popularity in the development of automated, closed-loop feedback systems for products and devices [1-3]. Current research is also focusing on the development of active hydrostatic bearings using mechatronic

control methods, which offer significantly higher efficiency compared to traditional open-loop systems. High reliability and machining accuracy depend heavily on the lubrication performance of mechanical bearings, which, as reported in various studies, can be

significantly enhanced through the optimization of their geometric design [4-6].

While optimizing the geometry of hydrostatic bearings can enhance lubrication performance, this improvement is typically a one-time benefit. Once the mechanical design is finalized, making further structural modifications becomes challenging. Consequently, alternative methods for improving lubrication performance are often favored. One such approach involves the use of active hydrostatic bearings, which incorporate active elements to enhance the fluid film's stiffness. Increased film stiffness leads to greater load-carrying capacity of the bearing. Generally, active hydrostatic bearings are classified into three configurations, based on the type of active input used to regulate the bearing's dynamic behavior

In the first configuration, viscosity is employed as the primary control input to actively regulate the lubrication performance of the bearing. To implement active lubrication in hydrostatic bearings, Hesselbach, Wang, and Zhang introduced the use of magnetorheological (MR) fluids controlled via an externally applied magnetic field. This field modifies the fluid's viscosity in real time, enabling the system to adjust the fluid film thickness according to changes in load. Despite this innovative approach, MR-fluid-based hydrostatic bearings face a major drawback: their ability to support only relatively low loads. Supporting heavier loads requires enlarging the bearing's contact area. Because of their ability to respond to external magnetic fields, hydrostatic bearings using MR fluids are typically known as smart bearings [7-9]. To enable active lubrication, Kumar employed a hybrid approach that combined tailored recess shapes with magnetorheological (MR) fluids [10].

The second configuration utilizes recess pressure as the input variable to control and track the clearance gap within the bearing. Fabian [11] and Morosi [12] introduced a jet-based approach to regulate the pressure within the clearance in the gap separating the rotating shaft and the inner surface of the bearing. The jet is actuated by a piezoelectric device and is used to regulate the recess pressure within the bearing. Mizumoto [13] introduced the concept of an active orifice for regulating recess pressure in hydrostatic bearings. Several researcher focus on the use of servo

valves to control the recess pressure [14-16]. Eberhardt [17] utilized an eddy current sensor to measure the clearance gap, activating the hydrostatic support when the gap reached a critical threshold. An active aerostatic thrust bearing was introduced by Rehman [18] in which recess pressure is regulated by high-speed pneumatic valves to vary the fluid film thickness as necessary. Various restrictor designs for managing recess pressure have been suggested by Kang [19, 20], including double-action restrictors with tapered and cylindrical spool configurations for achieving variable compensation in hydrostatic bearings. In a more recent study, Babin [21] experimentally introduced a servo-controlled thrust bearing aimed at enhancing dynamic stiffness under external loading. Additionally, Lai [22] implemented a membrane-based restrictor system to actively regulate lubrication by adjusting the recess pressure.

In the third setup, active lubrication is achieved by utilizing the supply pressure as a controllable input parameter. Santos [23] introduced the use of a hydraulic actuator to regulate the supply pressure, which in turn enhances both the stiffness and damping characteristics of the oil film. Similarly, San Andrés [24] proposed using an externally applied pressure source to improve fluid film stiffness in gas bearings. Enhanced stiffness in the fluid film contributes to vibration reduction in the rotor system and promotes greater operational stability. Santos [12] employed a linearized model based on the system's equilibrium point. However, hydrostatic bearings inherently exhibit strong nonlinear behavior due to the presence of the oil film, which acts as a nonlinear element. As a result, the use of a linearized model is only valid within a limited region near the equilibrium, and its ability to predict system performance beyond that range is limited. Nonlinear control is necessary to achieve a desired overall system performance. In order to improve a system's stiffness and damping coefficients, Waheed [11-13] combined bearing displacements and velocities as control inputs, ignoring trajectory tracking.

Current research nonlinear mathematical model for hydrostatic thrust bearing, and investigate three different types of control input such as viscosity, recess pressure and supply pressure. To verify effectiveness of proposed controlled scheme result are compared with published literature [25]. Compared to published

literature work in [25], fractional-order PID (FOPID) controllers have a number of benefits, such as increased flexibility, increased resilience to system fluctuations, and superior disturbance rejection. Particularly for model 2 in [25] which is of higher-order. FOPID controllers, which make use of fractional calculus, can offer a greater range of tuning parameters, resulting in more accurate control of dynamic systems and improved tracking responses. This paper is organized into the following sections: Section 2 details the mathematical formulation of hydrostatic thrust bearings, Section 3 introduces the FOPID controller design, Section 4 outlines the results, and Section 5 provides the conclusion.

2. Mathematical Models

2.1. Control Input Based on Fluid Viscosity

In Figure 1, a thrust bearing is presented that utilizes viscosity as a controllable input, usually regulated via an externally applied magnetic field.

Figure 1 Hydrostatic thrust bearing.

The motion characteristics of a hydrostatic thrust bearing can be represented by the following model:

$$M\ddot{h} = f + w \tag{1}$$

The distribution of pressure determines the oil film's force. Assume that the Reynolds equation [8] represents the pressure of the confined zone and assuming constant pressure within the recess region

$$\frac{h^3}{12\mu} \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) = \dot{h} \tag{2}$$

The following expression is obtained by applying the integration to Equation (2):

$$p(r) = C_1 \ln(r) + \frac{3\mu\dot{h}r^2}{(h+h_0)^3} + C_2 \tag{3}$$

Implementing the boundary conditions $p(R_1) = P_b$ and $p(R_2) = 0$ to Equation (3) leads to the following expression:

$$\begin{cases} C_1 \ln(R_1) + C_2 = P_b - \frac{3\mu\dot{h}R_1^2}{(h+h_0)^3} \\ C_1 \ln(R_2) + C_2 = 0 - \frac{3\mu\dot{h}R_2^2}{(h+h_0)^3} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Equation (4) can be solved and then substituted into Equation (3) to produce

$$p(r) = \ln(r) \frac{P_b(h+h_0)^3 - 3\mu\dot{h}(R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{(h+h_0)^3 \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2}} + \frac{3\mu\dot{h}r^2}{(h+h_0)^3} - \frac{P_b(h+h_0)^3 \ln R_2 - 3\mu\dot{h}(R_2^2 \ln R_2 - R_2^2 \ln R_1)}{(h+h_0)^3 \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2}} \tag{5}$$

The following is the expression for annular fluid force:

$$F_{annular} = 2\pi \int_{R_1}^{R_2} p(r) r dr \tag{6}$$

The following relationships provide the total fluid film force:

$$\begin{cases} f = F_{annular} + \pi R_1^2 P_b \\ f = \pi(R_1^2 - R_2^2) \frac{3\mu\dot{h}(R_1^2 + R_2^2) \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} - 3\mu\dot{h}(R_1^2 - R_2^2) + P_b(h+h_0)^3}{2 \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} (h+h_0)^3} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Equation (7) can be rearranged to produce the following expression when viscosity is used as a control input.

$$f = BP_b + \frac{A\dot{h}}{(h+h_0)^3} u_1 \tag{8}$$

Where

$$A = \pi(R_1^2 - R_2^2) \left[\frac{3(R_1^2 + R_2^2) \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} - 3(R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{2 \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2}} \right]$$

$$B = \frac{\pi(R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{2 \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2}}$$

A state space form is created by combining equations (1) and (8) and can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= F_1(x) + g_1(x)u_1 \\ Y &= CX \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Where, $F_1(x) = [\dot{h} \quad (BP_b + w)/M]^T$

$$g_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{Ah}{M(h+h_0)^3} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad C = [1 \quad 0]^T$$

2.2. Control Input Based on Active Supply Pressure

Model 2 input is based on active supply pressure as illustrated in Figure 2, the capillary-controlled hydrostatic thrust bearing is pressured by an externally applied active pressure supply.

Figure 2 Thrust Bearing Controlled by Active Supply Pressure.

The following is an expression for the input and output sections' flow rates:

$$\begin{cases} Q_{in} = \frac{\pi d^4 (P_s - P_b)}{128 \mu L} \\ Q_{out} = -\frac{\pi R_2 h^3}{6 \mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_2} \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

The following expression provides the continuity equation:

$$Q_{in} = Q_{out} + \pi R_2^2 \dot{h}$$

$$(11)$$

Equation (11) yields the following connection when the pressure distribution is substituted:

$$\frac{\pi d^4 (P_s - P_b)}{128 \mu L} + \frac{\pi P_b (h + h_0)^3 - 3 \pi \dot{h} \mu (R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{6 \mu \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2}} = 0 \tag{12}$$

Equation (12) is combined with Equations (1) and (8), yielding the state space form that follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= F_2(x) + g_2(x)u_2 \\ Y &= CX \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Where

$$F_2(x) = \frac{192 \left(-\frac{2}{3} w (h + h_0)^3 + \pi \mu \dot{h} (R_1^2 - R_2^2) \right) \left(L (h + h_0)^3 - \frac{3d^4}{64} \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} \right) + 9 \pi \mu \dot{h} d^4 (R_1 - R_2)^2 (R_1 + R_2)^2}{128 M (h + h_0)^3 \left(L (h + h_0)^3 - \frac{3d^4}{64} \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} \right)}$$

$$g_2(x) = -\frac{3 \pi d^4 (R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{128 M \left(L (h + h_0)^3 - \frac{3d^4}{64} \ln \frac{R_1}{R_2} \right)}, \quad C = [1 \quad 0]^T$$

Figure 3 Membrane-compensated hydrostatic bearing schematic.

2.3. Membrane-Controlled Thrust Bearing

An active membrane restrictor is included in this type to regulate recess pressure. Figure 3 displays the membrane-compensated hydrostatic thrust bearing concept.

The following expression [8] provides the flow into the hydrostatic bearing:

$$Q_{in} = \frac{\pi r (x + x_0)^3}{6 \mu} \frac{\partial p_{mem}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_2} - \pi r_2^2 \dot{x} \tag{14}$$

$$Q_{out} = -\frac{\pi R_2 h^3}{6 \mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_2} \tag{15}$$

The continuity equation for the hydrostatic thrust bearing is expressed as follows:

$$Q_{in} = Q_{out} + \pi R_2^2 \dot{h}$$

(16)

By inserting the pressure distribution into the equations (14)-(16), P_b can be determined

$$P_b = -\frac{\pi R_2 (h+h_0)^3}{6\mu} \left(\frac{6\mu \dot{h} R_2}{(h+h_0)^3} - \frac{3\mu \dot{h} (R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{R_2 (h+h_0)^3 (\ln R_1 - \ln R_2)} \right) + \pi R_2^2 \dot{h} + \pi r_2^2 \dot{x} + \frac{\frac{P_s (x+x_0)^3 + 3\mu \dot{x} (r_1^2 - r_2^2)}{(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2)} - 6\mu r_2^2 \dot{x}}{\frac{(x+x_0)^3}{(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2)} + \frac{(h+h_0)^3}{(\ln R_1 - \ln R_2)}} \quad (17)$$

State-space representation of a membrane-restrictor-controlled hydrostatic bearing is created by combining Equation (17) with Equations (1) and (8). The following expressions provide the state-space representation of the hydrostatic bearing controlled by a membrane restrictor:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= F_3(x) + g_3(x)u_3 \\ Y &= CX \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Where

$$F_3(x) = \left[\frac{A\mu}{M(h+h_0)^3} + \frac{B\pi(R_1^2 - R_2^2)}{2M(\ln R_1 - \ln R_2)} \right] \dot{h} + \frac{BP_s(x+x_0)^3}{M(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2) \left[\frac{(x+x_0)^3}{(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2)} + \frac{(h+h_0)^3}{(\ln R_1 - \ln R_2)} \right]} + \frac{Bw}{M}$$

$$g_3(x) = \frac{B\pi r_2^2}{M} + \frac{3\mu B(r_1^2 - r_2^2) - 6\mu r_2^2 B(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2)}{M(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2) \left[\frac{(x+x_0)^3}{(\ln r_1 - \ln r_2)} + \frac{(h+h_0)^3}{(\ln R_1 - \ln R_2)} \right]}$$

A detailed mathematical representation of the hydrostatic thrust bearing equipped with a membrane restrictor is displayed in equation (18).

3. Fractional order controller:

Podlubny was the first to introduce FOPID [26]. Such a controller's control law can be explained as

$$u(t) = k_p e(t) + k_i D_t^{-\lambda} e(t) + k_d D_t^\mu e(t) \quad (19)$$

where λ and μ stand for integral and differential power, respectively, and k_p, k_i and k_d for proportional, integral, and differential gains. The differential operator is denoted by $D_t^{-\mu}$, and the

fractional integral by $D_t^{-\lambda}$.

The FOPID controller's transfer function representation is

$$u(s) = k_p e(s) + k_i s^{-\lambda} e(s) + k_d s^\mu e(s) \quad (20)$$

The five tuning parameters of the FOPID controller are k_p, k_i, k_d, λ and μ . The FOPID controller has two extra parameters λ and μ , in contrast to a traditional PID controller.

A general depiction of a fractional order system's input-output is

$$y(t) = -\sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i D^{\alpha_i} y(t) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} b_j D^{\beta_j} u(t) \quad (21)$$

where n_a and n_b are the number of identifying coefficients and a_i and b_j are non-integer coefficients. Both α_i and β_j are positive noninteger values. The input and output of the system are denoted by $y(t)$ and $u(t)$. Equation (21)'s input-output model can be expressed in transfer function form as

$$G(s) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_b} b_j s^{\beta_j}}{1 + \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i s^{\alpha_i}} \quad (22)$$

In order to analyze the stability performance of FOPID controller with PID, we consider a closed-loop system with the fractional order plant $G(s)$ Eq. (22) and controller $u(s)$ as shown in Eq. (20), and then closed-loop characteristic equation can be written as

$$D(s) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i s^{\alpha_i} + (k_p + k_i s^{-\lambda} + k_d s^\mu) \sum_{j=0}^{n_b} b_j s^{\beta_j} = 0 \quad (23)$$

Stability of FOPID controller can be determine by optimal tuning of FOPID controller parameters k_p, k_i, k_d, λ and μ , so that all poles of $D(s)$ lies in the left half plane. The FOPID controller possesses more tuning parameters than the PID controller, resulting in a larger stability region. This enhances the controller's design flexibility, allowing it to achieve the desired performance and support more complex dynamic behavior. Additional advantages include the elimination of steady-state error, enhanced gain and phase margins, robustness to plant gain variations, and improved attenuation of high-frequency disturbances. However, the tuning of controller gains becomes more complex in the case of the FOPID

controller due to its increased parameter set. FOPID controller is tuned with matlab builtin genetic algorithm. The FOMCON toolbox in MATLAB is used to build and implement the FOPID controller [27]. The table for FOPID controller tuning parameters is given below;

Table 1 FOPID parameters

Parameters	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
	FOPID I	FOPID II	FOPID III
K_p	9×10^{-4}	0.1	35
K_i	9×10^{-5}	0.1	9×10^{-9}
K_d	2	8	15
λ	0.3	0.5	0.9
μ	1.01	1	1.1

The control law for equations (9), (13), and (18) will be given by;

$$u_i = \frac{1}{g_i(x)} \left[-F_i(x) - k_{pi}e(s) + k_{di}s^{-\lambda}e(s) + k_{di}s^{\mu}e(s) \right] \therefore i \in 1,2,3 \tag{24}$$

Where i belongs to model number, and tuning parameters is given in Table 1.

4. Results

In order to verify the efficacy of the suggested approach, Matlab/Simulink simulations were conducted. A number of steps and computations were completed prior to running the simulations. It involved considering initial values of h_0 , x_0 , \dot{h} , \ddot{h} , \dot{x} , \ddot{x} , and P_s , and the external load. The Simulink parameters listed in Sha et al [25] (Published literature) are used to run the simulations.

Figure 4 Simulink model for Model 1

Fluid viscosity is the control input in Model 1. Only when the initial velocity is not zero can the control law of Equation (24) apply to the model of Equation (9). The control input would reach an infinite value if the starting velocity was zero. The initial velocity is maintained at nonzero to prevent such situations. For the system model of Equation (9), the control law of Equation (24) is applied. Simulink model for model 1 alongwith FOPID controller is shown in Figure 4.

The supply pressure is $P_s = 1 \text{ Mpa}$, and the external load is $w = 1500 \text{ N}$. The results were compared to the literature that had already been published [25].

Figure 5 Tracking performance when viscosity is used as a control input

Figure 6 Simulink model for Model 2

Figure 5 illustrates the time-displacement response. The results validate that the developed mathematical model achieves the target fluid film thickness more quickly. Specifically, the rise time T_{r1} and settling time T_{s1} in this study are observed to be 1.11 seconds and 2.04 seconds, respectively. In contrast, the method described in [25] yields a rise time T_{r2} of 3.35 seconds and a settling time T_{s2} of 5.80 seconds. This

comparison clearly demonstrates that the proposed model offers a faster dynamic response in reaching the intended displacement h .

In Model 2, the supply pressure is utilized as the control input, while the output variable is the fluid film thickness. The external load is fixed at $w = 1000$ N. Two control strategies are implemented: the controller (as described by Sha et al. [25]) and the Fractional order FOPID controller proposed in this study. Simulink model for model 2 alongwith FOPID controller is shown Figure 6. As illustrated in Figure 7, FOPID controller demonstrates a quicker dynamic response—exhibiting reduced rise and settling times—compared to the controller referenced from the existing literature [25].

Figure 7 Tracking performance when supply pressure is used as a control input.

From Figure 8, it is evident that the proposed controller achieves improved performance by initiating a higher initial supply pressure and delivering faster tracking to reach the target fluid film thickness. Specifically, the rise time T_{r1} and settling time T_{s1} under the FOPID control are measured at 0.27 seconds and 0.49 seconds, respectively, whereas the method in [25] results in $T_{r2} = 0.54$ seconds and $T_{s2} = 0.97$ seconds. This comparison confirms that the proposed approach provides superior tracking speed in reaching the desired displacement or fluid film thickness.

Figure 8 supply pressure is used as a control input.

Model 3 introduces a hydrostatic thrust bearing regulated by a membrane restrictor, with fluid film thickness considered as the output variable. Simulations were conducted for both the proposed approach and the method presented in [25]. Simulink model for model 3 alongwith FOPID controller is shown Figure 9. As illustrated in Figure 10, the proposed control scheme demonstrates superior performance, exhibiting faster convergence as well as reduced rise and settling times in comparison to the previously reported method. the rise time T_{r1} and settling time T_{s1} under the FOPID control are measured at 0.39 seconds and 0.63 seconds, respectively, whereas the method in [25] results in $T_{r2} = 0.84$ seconds and $T_{s2} = 1.54$ seconds. This comparison confirms that the proposed approach provides superior tracking speed in reaching the desired displacement or fluid film thickness.

Figure 9 Simulink model for Model 3

Figure 10 tracking performance when hydrostatic bearing regulated by membrane restrictor.

5. Conclusions

This work presents a mechatronics control techniques for active lubrication in hydrostatic thrust bearings. Trajectory tracking control of the system presents significant challenges due to the sensitivity of the system response to the chosen control input. (a) When fluid viscosity is used as the control input, the system can be influenced primarily during the transient response phase. However, since the tunable range of magnetic fluid viscosity is inherently limited, the achievable tracking performance is also constrained. (b) Integrating an active restrictor into the system offers a cost-effective and practical method for trajectory control. Nonetheless, this approach introduces considerable complexity, making the overall control and tracking process more difficult. (c) Using supply pressure as the control variable allows for system linearization and the application of Fractional order control to enhance robustness. The trade-off, however, is the requirement for a complex active pressure supply system. Simulation results in MATLAB/Simulink confirm the effectiveness of the proposed fractional-order control strategies. Compared to previously published methods, the proposed approach exhibits superior dynamic behavior, as evidenced by reduced rise and settling times.

Nomenclature

R_1, R_2	Inner and outer radius for bearing
P_b	Recess pressure
r_1, r_2, r_3	Radius for membrane restrictor

μ	Fluid viscosity
P_s	Supply pressure
h_0	Initial fluid film thickness
h	Fluid film thickness

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